

Transformations in the System of Youth Values (on the Example of the Republic of Karakalpakstan)

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Abstract: *In this article, the authors have researched and defined the values of modern youth of the Republic of Karakalpakstan: what they live by, what they care about, what they strive for. In this work, young people of Karakalpakstan were considered as representatives of modern youth: students of colleges, lyceums, university students. The survey was conducted in all districts and the city of Nukus to create a complete picture of the values of youth.*

Key words: *Republic of Karakalpakstan, youth, values, preferences of modern Karakalpakstan youth, the transformation of values of modern youth.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

The prospective development of society is inextricably linked with the value orientations of modern youth, and they, in turn, are relevant values, especially in the era of globalization. Of course, the values of young people can change depending on socio-cultural changes and personal experience, since value orientations are interconnected with other processes and phenomena. They are also an element of such integral concepts as lifestyle, life position, social potential. «Young people, as an integral part of any society, involved in numerous processes of modernization and stabilization of society, are not only a kind of indicator of ongoing changes, but also form the potential of the future innovative society». [8] Young people, being significant in their numbers and potential, not only reproduce social relations and structure, but also perform an innovative function, introducing changes to the existing order, including accepted norms and standards of behavior, ideas about what is important and socially acceptable.

Values play an important role in the integration of society and the individual system, and the future life of society, its development in cultural and material terms, completely depends on the preferences of today's youth. Therefore, the question of the values of modern youth is becoming increasingly important.

The study of the value orientations of young people is also explained by the fact that this socio-demographic group is traditionally considered the most active; the present and future development of society is made dependent on the nature of the participation of the younger generation in it. The richness of life in terms of events, which implies the acquisition of one's status in the system of social relations, causes activity associated with the need to resolve issues of self-determination. [5]

At different periods of the historical development of each society, its own set of value orientations is formed, the system of which acts as the highest level of social regulation. The transformation of values of modern youth has a key influence on changing behavioral attitudes. [7]

Thus, the study of the value orientations of young people opens up access to understanding the motivation for the activities of certain social groups, and also helps to explain the specifics of social processes.

Therefore, in order to study the process of transformation of youth values in modern socio-economic conditions, in July-August 2024 we conducted a sociological study of the values of youth of the Republic of Karakalpakstan aged 14 to 30 years.

II. METHODS

The research method was a standardized interview at the place of residence. The sample was chosen randomly. The sample size was 962 respondents:

- Nukus city – 108;
- Nukus district – 82;
- Amu Darya district – 69;
- Biruni district – 78;
- Kegeyli district – 67;
- Kanlykul district – 39;
- Karauzak district – 43;
- Kungrad district – 81;
- Muynak district – 38;
- Takhtakupyr district – 58;
- Takhiatash district – 35;
- Turtkul district – 78;
- Khodjeyli district – 58;
- Shumanay district – 32;
- Chimbay district – 62;
- Ellikkala district – 34.

There was no division by gender as such because the study was conducted using a random sample, that is, respondents were stopped on the street and questioned if the respondent was between 14 and 30 years old at the time.

According to the results of the study, the majority of respondents are between the ages of 14 and 30.

In terms of the age quota of respondents, no requirements were put forward regarding the percentage ratio of the number of respondents surveyed belonging to each individual age category.

III. MAIN PART

To the question: "Tell me what education you have?" the answers were distributed as follows:

- Secondary – 18% of respondents (173 respondents);
- Incomplete higher education – 69% of respondents (664 respondents);
- Higher education – 13% of respondents (125 respondents).

According to the results of our study, the majority (69%) of respondents answered that they have an incomplete higher education. This suggests that these respondents are practically students of universities in our country. And 173 respondents (18%) are schoolchildren or respondents who graduated from colleges or gymnasiums.

If we explain the smaller number of respondents with higher education (13%), there could be several options:

- went to work part-time in other regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan or in other countries;
- perhaps they were at work during our survey and were unable to participate in our study.

To the question: "What is the most valuable thing in life for you?" the answers are distributed as follows:

1. family - 74.3%;
2. health - 54.1%;
3. interesting work - 44.2%;
4. materially secure life - 58.4%;
5. love - 43.9%.

Although the results obtained indicate that at the present stage there has been some change in the values of modern youth compared to the values of previous generations, it is still worth noting that in the hierarchy of values of modern youth, family, love, and education remain the most important.

Philosopher I.S. Kon, drawing attention to one of the aspects of the activity of the modern family, points out that "changes in society – scientific, technical, cultural, everyday – are so rapid and significant that today's children will have to live in a world different from the one in which their parents live. Therefore, the effectiveness of raising the younger generation should be assessed not so much by whether we were able to prepare them to act independently and make decisions in conditions that obviously did not exist and could not exist in the life of the parental generation, but by what spiritual and moral values and priorities were formed". [4]

Of course, it is necessary to take into account that the transformations primarily affect young people as the most dynamic and receptive to new socio-demographic groups. Despite the fact that economic reforms have been carried out, and our republic has embarked on the path of establishing market relations, and the previously existing value priorities have faded into the background, yielding leading positions to economic and material values, at the same time the younger generation, adapting to the changed reality, retains the basic "framework" of their values and stereotypes. Basic spiritual values - collectivism, the priority of the spiritual over the material, etc. - have not changed in general, although under certain conditions the previous values have become actualized in a modified, transformed form. In this regard, I would like to recall the words of T. Roosevelt, who wrote: "To educate without instilling moral principles is to raise another threat to society". [5]

Thus, it was revealed that modern Karakalpakstan youth attach great importance to family, care about their health, about a materially secure life, strive for higher education and career success, self-realization and financial independence.

In the hierarchy of merits, modern Karakalpakstan youth chose:

- In first place among respondents, by a wide margin, is family (94%), that is, they attach great importance to the person who takes care of his family;
- Friendship is of great importance to survey participants (87%), that is, a person you can trust, someone you can rely on in difficult times;
- health (88%), that is, a person must have a sense of concern for his health and the health of his family members;
- education (81%) – a person must be educated, cultured, and well-read;
- In the survey, 18% of respondents rated hard work as a virtue and as an activity that provides an opportunity for self-realization;
- highly rated independence and autonomy, respondents value the opportunity to make independent decisions provided by one or another type of activity, freedom to choose forms and methods of activity – 47%;
- kindness as a superhuman virtue was emphasized by 76.7%;
- also, decency - 65%;
- honesty - 71.1%;
- Intelligence as a human virtue was emphasized by 56.3%.

In the course of the study, respondents answered the open-ended question: “What is your idea of happiness?” as follows:

- a happy and prosperous family – 88%;
- an interesting and stable job – 63%;
- friends, family and loved ones – 59%;
- getting a higher education – 72%;
- a peaceful sky above your head, so that there is no war throughout the world – 13%;
- a fair state and a fair society – 34%.

This sociological study of young people shows the existence of persistent ideas that higher education provides greater opportunities in terms of employment and salary. When choosing a job, young people are guided by the size of their earnings and the content, that is, the job should, first of all, be well-paid and interesting. Here it is necessary to emphasize the interests of young people, directed primarily towards those areas of employment in which prestige and income levels are higher. The most important components of work motives are: salary level (91%), opportunity to work (73%), prospects for career growth (68%). However, 40% of respondents are not sure that they will work in their specialty.

The answers to the question: “What do you need most to be happy?” also correlate with the previous answers. In order to be happy, it is necessary to have a prosperous family, to love and be loved by loved ones and relatives, to have a good job, to have wealth, material goods and financial stability, to be an educated and healthy person, also to have communicative values and the value of communication, to be free and independent, to have the opportunity for self-realization (both

through education and through employment). It is also important for young people to feel personal security, prestige and fame, to realize themselves in creativity, and to have faith in something greater.

As can be seen from the above, young people give a large place to family values in their lives. Material values also have a high rating among young people, including as a means of achieving family well-being. This material and financial orientation of young people can be explained by the fact that the current young generation was born in an era of global change.

During this study, the answers to the question about the interests, hobbies, and passions of today's youth were somewhat disappointing. For example, 87% of respondents had virtually no interests. They were completely engrossed in hanging out on social networks. Although this phenomenon can also be attributed to the interests of modern youth. Of course, the Internet and social networks contribute to the development of intensive virtual communication and the intellectualization of individual leisure, but at the same time, due to the fact that remote communication is often anonymous, they expose young people to a high risk of manipulation.

It should be noted that many sociological studies have recorded an increase in the time that young people spend listening to audio and watching videos, using various channels of mass communication. "Hanging out" on networks is not only a compensation for the lack of communication, a way of self-realization, an alternative to creativity, a channel for "letting off steam" (the opportunity to satisfy gambling inclinations or release accumulated discontent), but also a form of social maladjustment, an escape from the problems and difficulties of real life.

Thus, only 13% of respondents have interests in reading and sports, and several people noted that they are interested in sewing and baking (mostly girls). But it is impossible to classify the 87% of respondents as deviants, they are simply most interested in social networks: they receive data for their work or study, communicate virtually with their friends in other countries, find interesting materials about their homeland and its culture.

In our study, special attention was paid to the attitude of Karakalpakstan youth towards religion. It was found that in the public consciousness of young people there is a lack of increased interest in a religious way of life. Among the respondents, 11% - approximately 105 people - turned out to be true believers: of these, 38 girls wore hijabs and 67 young men wore beards, thus indicating that they are true believers. Although 79% of respondents noted that they believe in God, they are not attracted to the religious way of life.

Thus, we can conclude that modern Karakalpakstan youth demonstrate a balanced and adequate attitude towards religion, that the public consciousness of the youth of Karakalpakstan is not characterized by an increased interest in the religious way of life. For example, some studies show that our youth are aware of the importance of religious knowledge and also strive for spiritual development. Young people turn to religion primarily from the point of view of its compensatory function; they see it to a greater extent as the basis of morality, the guardian of national traditions and culture. But, on the other hand, we consider it necessary to carry out educational work among our youth so that false, distorted information related to religious extremism is not spread.

In political terms, our Karakalpakstan youth shows a certain interest. One of the key characteristics of the political consciousness of our youth is the desire to be informed. The younger generation actively uses modern media: The Internet, social networks, online platforms. This allows them to be more informed about political events both within the country and around the world. Of course, such accessibility of information contributes to the development of critical thinking and analytical skills in young people. However, the influence of family, education and culture on the formation of political consciousness is also significant. Traditional values and cultural characteristics play an

important role in how young people perceive politics and social processes. Family values and education can form the basis for understanding politics, influencing how young people perceive political events. Currently, in our republic there is an increase in attention to political activity among young people. For example, youth organizations (Youth Union) and student initiatives become platforms for discussing politics, exchanging opinions and actively participating in public life (Youth Parliament). Naturally, this indicates a growing interest among young people in politics and their desire to contribute to the development of the country. However, most young people prefer to stay away from politics, focusing on personal and professional aspects of life. To the question: “What is your attitude towards politics?” many respondents answered that they do not want to interfere in politics (76%); for them, personal space is more important: family, work, friends. Although other young people actively participate in political discussions and initiatives – 12%. The remaining 12% of respondents abstained.

Thus, the political consciousness of Karakalpakstan youth is still in the process of active development and transformation. Of course, its future depends on the combination of traditional values with modern challenges, awareness, active participation and the desire to create a favorable social environment for all citizens of our republic.

To the question: “Do you take part in the improvement of the city/district?” the answers were distributed as follows:

- I take part in cleaning the area – 69%;
- I never litter, I try not to litter – 73%;
- I campaign for the cleanliness of the city/district – 13%;
- I don’t care about it, it’s not my job – 4%;
- We constantly spend our time on cleanup days – 89%;
- Difficult to answer – 17%.

Thus, the largest number of respondents who regularly spend their time on clean-up days are young students. Also, respondents who try not to litter are young people, who also belong to the studying youth, according to our assumption. Young people who take an active part in cleaning the territory are presumably city residents, since in the city of Nukus certain actions to clean the territory are held in the mahallas: clean-up days, khashars¹.

The majority of our youth – 58% – think little about the meaning of life. They believe that these are philosophical questions for which there is currently no time; they need to work and study in order to ensure not only their own future, but also that of their families. And such questions are considered idle for them. Some respondents – 19% – believe that such questions, which have no answers, can lead a person to suicide, parasitism, relaxation, laziness. Almost a quarter of respondents – 23% – found it difficult to answer this question; for them, this question is completely incomprehensible. Maybe this is a lack of education at school? Or maybe this wasn’t talked about in the family? Perhaps this is a lack of horizons, since many of the respondents surveyed (almost 69%) do not read books. Although they value the traditions and customs of their people, they have some aspirations in life. Karakalpakstan youth value family ties and education. Modern young people also strive for self-realization and development of their talents.

To the question: “What would you most like to achieve in life?” the respondents’ answers were distributed as follows:

¹ Khashars are voluntary organized actions of the people for various reasons. For example, cleaning the territory, picking cotton, building a house for young poor families, holding events.

- Family happiness - 78%;
- Becoming a qualified specialist - 71%;
- Being free and independent - 61%;
- Peace and the opportunity not to interfere in anything - 58%;
- Wealth - 51%;
- True love - 47%;
- Having the opportunity to realize your talent - 35%;
- Power - 33%;
- Fame - 29%;
- Making a career - 28%;
- Difficult to answer - 7%.

Thus, the first priority is again to achieve family happiness. This suggests that traditional family upbringing still prevails in our society. Becoming a qualified specialist is to ensure your future, and the future is associated with family happiness, all this suggests that our youth puts family values above all else.

IV. CONCLUSION

Overall, the survey results showed that modern youth, for the most part, perceive value orientations as certain goals, something they want to achieve, something they want to possess. Be it family, work or creative success. Having analyzed the respondents' statements, we ranked the types of values they proposed, and we saw that young people are interested not only in money and material goods, as many sometimes believe. Spiritual values, such as faith and creativity, turned out to be more important than material ones. As for success, modern youth believe that the greatest help in achieving it will come from the personal qualities and creative potential of the youth themselves.

Thus, the study of the transformation of values and guidelines of modern youth is becoming increasingly important every day. In some matters, young people are already quite mature and serious, but in others they are still naive and, to some extent, limited. Modern Karakalpakstan youth are characterized by both spiritual and moral values, as well as purely pragmatic, material values of life. All of them occupy a significant place in the value space of the personality of a modern young person. Among the vital values of young people, the most popular are health, well-being, having true friends and love. These values ensure the harmonious and complete development of the young person's personality.

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